

Juan Yacht Design: Testing LES turbulence models in race boat sails

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Abstract

The objective of this project is to implement LES turbulence models outside the academic world to simulate flow around sails to replace RANS models that are the standard in the industry. The implementation and testing in the finite code ALYA is done by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center so that Juan Yatch Design SL (JYD) can appreciate the advantages of using a LES formulation for their problem. The obtained results show that LES can provide significant advantages over RANS simulation; at least for the cases we have studied. There is a significant difference in the predicted forces that can be related to the fact that RANS can not accurately capture two vortices created at the top and bottom of the Genoa sail.

1. Introduction

Yatch Design SL (JYD) is a Spanish company that specializes in the design of sail boats. Its main market is race boats for the most important competitions in the world: America's cup and Volvo Ocean Race. It has designed the boats for ABM AMRO, Ericsson and Groupama teams that have won the Volvo Ocean Race. The company treats all of the aspects of the boat design: structural analysis, sail aerodynamics, hull hydrodynamics and boat construction specifications and drawings. For both aerodynamics and hydrodynamics, the pioneering adoption of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) as a key ingredient of the design process has been one of main advantages with respect to the other companies in the field. JYD was one of the first companies to step from potential flow solvers to the use of Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) turbulence models that can acceptably predict the viscous forces for attached flows. This has as enabled the company to put aside the need for towing tank experimental tests. For the simulation of the flow around the boat the company initially used the CFD code COMET [8] initially developed by Professor Milovan Peric at Hamburg University. COMET was then bought by CD adapco and converted into a commercial software. Lately it has been discontinued and its functionalities have been incorporated into the STAR-CCM+. This is the code currently used by JYD for its CFD simulations. The company has a computer cluster with several cores on which it runs the simulations. Nevertheless due to scalability problems, the high cost of the licenses, and the great number of simulations needed to design a boat the runs never use more than one node.

JYD's market is clearly a very competitive one. In order to stay ahead the company needs to have access to the latest technological developments in its field. The early adoption of RANS CFD has been a key competitive advantage that has contributed to a leading position in the market and important victories for its clients. Nowadays commercial RANS CFD codes have become more accessible to the competence and stepping to more innovative simulation tools would help JYD maintain its leadership. RANS models work well for most problems but their accuracy is reduced when there are important regions of separated flow. This happens at the boat sails for certain wind directions. Large eddy Simulation (LES) turbulence models are needed for such flows. This models require significantly higher computational resources than RANS models. In order to make LES models

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useful at the non-academic (industrial) level, highly parallel codes and HPC resources are mandatory. The commercial software licenses are charged per number of cpus used. Therefore, even if problems with the parallelization of the code can be solved, the cost of the licenses makes their use not feasible for LES simulations. The Computer Applications in Science & Engineering (CASE) department at BSC-CNS develops its own HPC CFD code, Alya, that already includes LES turbulence models. The proposed HPS solution involves applying Alya to solve the flow around the sails for challenging wind directions where the results obtained with RANS models have provided poor accuracy. The objective is to provide the company with a tool that can provide it with a new competitive advantage and prove the advantages of the use of real HPC power. Moreover it will open the possibility of exploring future collaborations.

As mentioned earlier, for a company in such a competitive market, striking first with a new technology is key to be a leader in the market. Of all the simulations the aero ones are particularly important because the sails are what the sailors pay more attention to when sailing, they are the engine of the boat. Sailors are continuously changing the sail setup in the same way they are constantly helming the boat. For this reason being able to simulate the flow around the sails with greatest details would translate into better helping the clients use their boats. Since this is the most important part for the sailors having an edge in on the aero would put the company in an advantage to the eyes of the clients.

2. Alya and the numerical tools used

Alya (see for instance [1–4, 9]) is the BSC in-house HPC-based multi-physics simulation code. It is one of the two Computational Fluid Dynamics codes in the Prace Benchmark suite but it can solve a wide range of problems among which we can mention: solids, thermal problems, combustion and chemical reactions. It is designed from scratch to run efficiently in parallel supercomputers, solving coupled problems. The target domain is engineering, with all its particular features: complex geometries and unstructured meshes, coupled multi-physics with exotic coupling schemes and Physical models, ill-posed problems, flexibility needs for rapidly including new models, etc. Since its conception in 2004, Alya has shown excellent scaling behaviour in an increasing number of cores, for example scaling up to 100.000 cores in Blue Waters, the NCSA supercomputer. It's main features are the following:

- It solves discretized partial differential equations (PDEs), preferring variational methods (particularly Finite Elements).
- Space discretization is based on unstructured meshes, with several types of elements (in our examples we shall use meshes with linear tetrahedra, prisms and pyramids).
- Both explicit and implicit time advance schemes are programmed. (in our examples we shall use implicit BDF schemes).
- Depending on the case, staggered or monolithic schemes are programmed. However, staggered schemes with coupling iterations are preferred for large multi-physics problems.
- Parallelization is based on mesh partitioning (for instance using Metis) and MPI tasks, which is specially well-suited for distributed memory machines.
- Alya sparse linear algebra solvers are specifically developed, with a tight integration with the overall parallelization scheme. There are no third-parties solver libraries required.

3. CFD model

The solution of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations can be coupled to both RANS and LES turbulence models. The time discretization is based on a second order backward differentiation formula (BDF) scheme and the linearization is carried out using the Picard method. The space discretization is based on the variational multiscale method (VMS) and is extensively described in [5]. At each time and linearization iteration a system for the velocity and pressure nodal unknowns is solved. The direct solution of the system is usually referred to as monolithic scheme. In order to avoid the use of complex preconditioners to account for the velocity-pressure coupling involved in this monolithic system, an algebraic fractional scheme was developed [1]. This scheme enables to segregate the solutions of the velocity and pressure at the algebraic level, by solving the pressure Schur complement using an iterative method (herein the Orthomin(1)). This strategy offers two main advantages. Firstly, with respect to the monolithic scheme, one shot of the method involves the solution of the momentum equation and the solution of a symmetric system for the pressure Laplacian representing the continuity equation. The momentum equations usually converge very well, even with a simple diagonal preconditioner. The

continuity equation is solved with the Deflated Conjugate Gradient solver (DCG) [6], together with a linelet preconditioner when anisotropic boundary layers [7] are present. Secondly, with respect to classical fractional step methods, no fractional errors are introduced and the solution converges to the same as the monolithic one. What is important to note here is that the solution strategy which consists in solving the pressure Schur complement instead of attacking directly the monolithic scheme, should be understood as part of the algebraic solution strategy of the Navier-Stokes system, and not a fancy trick to escape from this scheme.

4. LES and RANS turbulence modeling

Reynolds Average Navier Stokes turbulence models obtain a stationary solution that is representative of the mean flow. They model the effect of the fluctuating flow on the mean flow. Therefore they have limited application to transient simulation. Moreover they provide poor results when there are important separated regions. On the other hand, they are much cheaper computationally than LES simulations; at least 1 order of magnitude. They are also more robust and easier to use than LES models. Therefore they have wide spread use in the industry and are available in most commercial CFD codes. Alya includes several RANS models. The most popular are: SST k-omega, Spalart Allmaras and k-epsilon. The first one will be used in this work since it is the one typical used at Juan Yacht Design.

Large Eddy Simulation involves transient simulations with at least 2nd order time accurate methods. Also higher accuracy (less diffusive numerical schemes) in space are needed. The evolution of the Large Eddies is simulated and only the small eddies are modelled. The results must be averaged over large time periods of time. They have a much higher computational cost than RANS models. Therefore highly scalable and efficient codes are required. LES can not be used to model the flow close to the wall for High Reynolds problems due to computational cost. (At least for the next 2 decades). Wall Laws models are needed close to the wall. Several eddy viscosity turbulence models are implemented in Alya. For this work the WALE model shall be used. Moreover the variational multiscale method (VMS) can act as an implicit LES model where no additional turbulent viscosity is needed. We have also tested this option in this work and it gave very similar results to the WALE model but was slightly less robust.

5. Numerical Results

In this section we present the numerical results. Two main cases have been run. Initially only the three sails and the mast were simulated. Once this case was well understood and a satisfactory convergence was obtained, following the suggestions from JYD, the boat hull was also included to make the results more realistic. The observed behaviour was very similar so we shall concentrate mainly on the case with hull.

Figure 1- Boat geometry coloured with the pressure

A mesh with 6 million nodes and 33 million elements was used. It consisted mainly of tetrahedras and prisms plus some pyramids when needed. The time step size used was 0.005 seconds. The same case was run with a WALE LES model and an SST K-omega RANS model. For the LES model a second order time accurate method (BDF2) was used. In the RANS case since we are only interested in the steady result a BDF1 time scheme was used.

Details on the architecture chosen are described on Section 6. Both Blue Gene and Sandy Bridge machines were tested. The parallelism was obtained using MPI. For the cases we have used we have observed nearly linear

scalability up to 1024 processors but Alya (that as already mentioned is part of the Prace benchmark suite) has proved its scalability up to 130000 processors on SuperMuc. Actually this has been somehow a by product of this project. Since we were using SuperMuc for this project we were offered the possibility of testing our code on the whole machine.

Typical runs would run for 48 hours on 1024 processors. Then, depending on the how much they had advanced, the runs could be restarted. For the project we have been allocated 100000 hours on Marenostrom and 250000 on Juqueen, Fermi and SuperMuc. The amount of data produced depended on the frequency with which the results we output and the amount of results per time step. For a 33 million element and 6.6 million node mesh each scalar result weighted approximately 50 megabytes and 3D vector result 3 times more. A typical run could be 200000 steps with a post-processing frequency of 1000 steps.

In Figure 1 we show the geometry we have simulated coloured with the pressure from the LES results. In Figure 2 we present the temporal evolution of the force in the x direction (aligned with the boat motion) for the Genoa sail (the big one in the front) that produces most of the force. The case we have analysed has been chosen the company JYD as a representative case where RANS models do not give very accurate results. The contribution from the other two sails is approximately one order of magnitude smaller.

Figure 2- Forces on the genoa sail in the direction of the boat velocity

It can be observed that the RANS results converge to a force that is approximately 15 percent lower than the one for the LES case. Despite there are no experimental values for this sails, from the feedback obtained from the sailors, JYD confirmed that the RANS simulations typically under-predict the forces for such cases.

Figure 3- Qvorticity isosurfaces coloured by velocity modulus – boat hull and sails coloured by pressure

Qvorticity isosurfaces for the LES case are shown in Figures 3 and 4. Two important vortices are created at the top and bottom of the Genoa sail. This two vortices are poorly predicted by the RANS model. The centre of the vortex generates a region of low pressure. Figure 5 shows two horizontal cuts for the pressure close to the top and bottom of the Genoa sail. Instantaneous and average values for the LES case are presented together with the steady state RANS solution. The average LES results should be comparable with the RANS results. It can be observed that the low pressure region corresponding to the centre of the bottom vortex is not captured by the RANS simulation. For the upper vortex the RANS simulation can capture something but it is clearly more diffusive than the LES run. It can be concluded that the more diffusive behaviour of the RANS model can not capture the two main vortex correctly. This leads to a lower prediction of the pressure that affects the pressure on the sails and results in 15 percent difference for the forces on the sails.

Figure 4- Qvorticity isosurfaces coloured by velocity modulus – boat hull and sails coloured by pressure

6. Testing on four Tier-0 European supercomputers

For this project we have been given access to four Tier-0 European supercomputers. Marenostrum, SuperMUC, Fermi and Juqueen. The first two machines are SandyBridge with approximately 21 Gflops per core and the last two are Blue Gene with approximately 12 Gflops per core. This has been a very good opportunity to test Alya with the same problem on the four supercomputers. This had not been done before. On the initial tests, Alya was 8 times slower on BlueGene supercomputers compared to SandyBridge ones. A partial solution has been to run 4 MPI processes per core on Blue Gene machines. This increases the speed 2.2 times. Blue Gene machines are still 3.6 times slower than SandyBridge machines. This is more than one would expect looking at Gflops only and should be explored further.

7. Conclusions

The problem has been simulated with both LES and RANS techniques. After some tweaking of the numerical strategy and the mesh, good convergence has been obtained with Alya. Significant differences in the forces have been observed with LES and RANS methods. The pressure depends on the chosen turbulence model. RANS cannot predict the vortices correctly due to too much dissipation. The presented results show that LES could be an interesting tool in the short to medium term.

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Figure 5- Horizontal cuts for the pressure at two different heights. Instantaneous LES results(top), Average LES results(middle), steady state RANS (bottom)